

ISic2706

I.Sicily inscription 2706

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contr. Diana

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea"

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334519

1. Ἡδυχρ-
2. [ὦ] Ἀρχύ-
3. λιος.
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645126

PHI 334519

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 416

Calderone, S. 1949. Analecta epigraphica liparensia. *Epigraphica*. 11: 49-60. At 51 no.2

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